

STUDING MEDICINAL PLANTS (PHYTONYMS) IN THE SECTION OF PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation. This article will discuss the methods of easy study and teaching students of higher medical educational institutions the names of medicinal plants (phytonyms) in the discipline of Latin and medical terminology in the section of pharmaceutical terminology

Key words: phytonyms, pharmaceutical terminology, botanical terms

Indeed, there is a special charm in our land of the highest mountains, green valleys, forests, rivers and lakes, and even deserts. Especially due to its location in a region where several biogeographic regions intersect, the plant world is characterized by its extremely colorful nature. Generous nature proportionates the whole being in life. All living creatures in it live, flourish, multiply and, if necessary, take ointments from each other, enjoy the sources of vital needs. From this it can be understood that every creature in nature, every plant has its own healing property.

There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. These are used in scientific and folk medicine from about 120 plant species growing and cultured in natural conditions. Currently, about 40-47% of medicines used in medicine are obtained from plant raw materials. The study of medicinal plant names (phytonyms) in Latin according to the pharmaceutical nomenclature requires its healing properties. Another important aspect is that plant names are necessarily written in initials in Latin. Under the term phytonym (Greek phyton-plant +onym-name), the names of plants are understood.

Phytonyms are distinguished from other layers in the vocabulary by their direct connection with the history of socio-political, cultural development of the people, their interaction with customs and traditions. In the course of Latin and medical terminology, the study of botanical names is the assimilation of new linguistic materials with many lexical units, which can be ambiguous concepts, and students, as a rule, may not have an associative understanding of this topic. Phytonyms are a part of the language that has a long history. In addition to folk life, culture, history, socio-political views, they preserve the ancient traditions inherent in the language and language of the people who created them.

Plants can also be called differently in different oases of the same country, and the etymology of botanical names is always interesting and multifaceted. The task of Latin teachers is to create motivational conditions for students to consciously learn the names of plants in Latin. In the study of botanical terms, it is necessary to start with the introduction of words in Latin, since when the Latin term fully or partially corresponds to the corresponding word of the Uzbek language, students easily understand and remember the Uzbek equivalent.

For example, "Aloe" is translated as "Aloe" in Latin, "aloy" in Russian, and "aloes" in English, another example of this is "medicinal valerian", "medicinal speedwell", "medicinal calendula (marigold)", "medicinal borago", "kalankhoe", "mountain arnica" and

other plants. It is easy to remember the names of this medicinal plant, since in many languages it is written in the same way.

When a student knows the basic 6 different color names in medical terms, he will quickly and easily remember the name of the plants associated with that color name from Latin to Uzbek. For example, depending on the color of some plant flowers: Bryonia **alba**-white bronnia, Lamium **album**-white lamium, Viscum **album**-white mistletoe, Salix **alba**-white willow, Melilotus **albus**- melilot white (Latin **albus**-white), Centaurea **cyanus**- blue beetle (Greek **cyano**-blue), Crataegus **sanguineus**- red Hawthorn (**sanguineus**- blood color), Ribes **nigrum**-black currant, Populus **nigra**-black birch tree,(Latin **niger**-black) Aronia **melanocarpa**-black-fruited aronia (Greek **melano**-black, **carpus**-fruit), Polemonium **coeruleum**-blueberry (Latin **coeruleus**-blue), Nuphar **lutea**-yellow nufar (Latin **luteus**-yellow), Viola **tricolor**-tricolor violet (Latin **tri**-three, **color**-colour), Eucalyptus **cinerea**-grey eucalyptus (Latin **cinereus**-grey), Rhodiola **rosea**- Rhodiola pink, (Latin **roseus**-pink); the names of plants by their place of passage: Equisetum **arvense**- Equisetum field, Fragaria **vesca**- Wild strawberries, Oxycoccus **palustris**- Marsh cranberries, the names of countries: Atractylodes **chinensis**- atractilodes **Chinese**, Atractylodes **japonica**- Atractilodes **Japanese**, Berberis **amurensis**- **Amur** barberry, Bergenia **pacifica**- Bergenia **Pacific**, Dioscorea **caucasica**-Dioscorea of the **Caucasus**, Pinus **koreansis**-**Korean** pine, Patrinia **sibirica**-Patrinia **Siberian**; looking at the shape of the plants, for example: Achillea **millefolium**-Yarrow, (Latin **mille**-thousand, **folium**-leaf), Bergenia **crassifolia**- Bergenia thick - leaved, (Latin **crassus**-thick, **folium**-leaf), Betula **platyphilla**- flat-leaved birch, (Greek **platy**-plain, **phillo**-leaf), Chelidonium **majus**- Celandine large, (Latin **major**, **majus**-large), Leonurus **cardiaca**- Motherwort, (Latin **cardiacus**-cordial), Eucalyptus **globulus**- eucalyptus globules- (Latin **globulus**-spherical), Tilia **cordata**-Linden (lime-tree) heart-shaped (Latin cor, cordis-heart); plant names depending on the ingredients: Mentha **piperita**- Peppermint, (Latin piper-pepper); Artemisia **absinthium**-Wormwood bitter (Latin **absinthius**-bitter); depending on the seasons, for example: Rosa **majalis** (Latin **majalis**- may date), Primula **veris**- Primula (Latin **primus**-first, **ver**-spring) and others can be exemplified. Through these analogies, the student can easily remember phytonyms.

Good mastery of pharmaceutical terms is aimed at training professionals with universal knowledge, who can understand medical terms in their field well, which will help them think independently, critically and creatively, develop beliefs and motivate them to confidently enter into social relationships, regardless of the profession chosen by them.

References:

- 1.M.A.Juraeva Atlas of medicinal plants Tashkent, 2019
- 2.THE EASY WAYS OF LEARNING MEDICAL PLANTS (PHYTONYMS) IN THE DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY. KM Nematilloeyvna JournalNX 7 (06), 274-277
- 3.Bakayev, N. B., Shodiev, S. S., Khafizova, M. N., & Ostonova, S. N. (2020). SHAKESPEARS LEXICON: REASON WORD AS A DESIGN OF THE CONCEPT OF THE ABILITY OF THE HUMAN MIND TO ABSTRACTION, CONCLUSION. Theoretical & Applied Science, (6), 162-166.
- 4.Nematilloeyvna, K. M. The Easy Ways of Learning Medical Plants (Phytonyms) in the Department of Pharmaceutical Terminology. JournalNX, 7(06), 274-277.

- 5.Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF MICROCIRCULATION DISORDERS. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 60–65. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/2811>
- 6.Juraeva , DN, va Narzulaeva , UR (2022). Trigeminal nevrogiya hujumi paytida vegetativ o'zgarishlarning gender farqlari . AKADEMIKA: An Xalqaro Ko'p tarmoqli Tadqiqot Jurnal , 12(5), 322-326.
- 7.Pokhrel , S. va Chhetri , R. (2021). COVID-19 pandemiyasining o'qitish va o'rganishga ta'siri bo'yicha adabiyotlar sharhi. Yuqori ta'lim uchun the kelajak , 8(1), 133-141.
- 8.Нарзулаева, У., Самиева, Г., & Насирова, Ш. (2023). Гемореологические нарушения на ранних стадиях гипертензии в жарком климате. Журнал биомедицины и практики, 1(1), 221–225. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-1-31>
- 9.Hikmatullaeva , A. S., Raximov, R. A., Abduqadirova , M. A., Egamova , I. N., & Yarmuxamedova , N. A. (2020). Sovremenno predstavlenie o virusnoy infektsiya. Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya, (22-2 (100)), 58-66.
- 10.Raximova, V. Sh., & Yarmuxamedova , N. A. (2021). NEKOTORYE ASPEKTY PORAJENIYA PECHENI PRI SARS-COV-2. Biologiya, 1, 125.
- 11.Oripova , O. O., Samieva , G. U., Xamidova , F. M., & Narzulaeva , U. R. (2020). Sostoyanie plotnosti raspredeleniya limfoidnyx kletok slisistoy obolochki gortani va proyavleniya mestno immuna pri xroncheskom laringite (tahlil seksionnogo material). Akademiya, (4 (55)), 83-86.
11. Qobilovna, A. M. (2023). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(09), 32-44.
12. Ataullayeva, M. (2023). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AS A FACTOR OF PERSONAL AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A FUTURE SPECIALIST. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 109-114.
- 13.Qobilovna, A. M. (2021). BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QITUVCHILARIDA KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPITENTLIK SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK DETERMINANTLARI. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), (Special Issue), 102-105.
- 14.Ахмедова, М. (2020). НАРУШЕНИЯ ЭНДОТЕЛИАЛЬНОЙ ФУНКЦИИ ПРИ РАЗВИТИИ АФТОЗНОГО СТОМАТИТА. Достижения науки и образования, (18 (72)), 65-69.
- 15.Axmedova Malika Qilichovna. (2023). THE IMPACT OF SOCIOCULTURAL FACTORS ON THE PERVASIVENESS OF DENTAL CARIES AS A COMPLEX HEALTH CONDITION IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF MEDICAL SCIENCES AND CLINICAL RESEARCH, 3(9), 24–28.
- 16.Axmedova, M. (2023). USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY AT THE STAGES OF DIAGNOSIS AND PLANNING ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT BASED ON ENDOSSEAL IMPLANTS. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(11), 54-58.
- 17.Ostonova, G. (2023). ICHKI SEKRETSIYA BEZLARI FIZIOLOGIYASI. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(10 Part 3), 110-115.
- 18.Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI, 3(9), 126-130.
- 19.Rakhimovna, T. D., & Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. Conferencea, 9-14.

- 20.Rahimova, G. (2023). MAKTABLARDA BIOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 2, Выпуск 10, сс. 103–109).Zenodo.
- 21.Djalilova, Z. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY: ESSENCE, CHARACTERISTICS AND EFFICIENCY. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(23), 29-38.
- 22.Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE AND POSITION OF TEACHING METHODS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(10), 31-42.
- 23.Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL CASE. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(14), 9-15.
- 24.Джалилова, З. (2023). The notion of illocution in the theory of speech acts by John Austin. Современные тенденции при обучении иностранному языку в XXI веке, 1(1).
- 25.Obidovna, D. Z. (2023). ADAPTING TEACHING METHODS TO MODERN EDUCATIONAL TRENDS: PEDAGOGICAL ASPECT. International Journal of Pedagogics, 3(10), 72-77.
- 26.Musayeva, A. (2023). MADANIYATSHUNOSLIK YONDASHUVI ASOSIDA TALABA-YOSHLARNING KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 9), 97-99.
- 27.Караматовна, М. А. (2023). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ В ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИИ ТЕОРИИ СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОГО ПОЛЯ. Мусаева, А. (2023). РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК В МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ СРЕДЕ. Современная наука и исследования, 2 (4), 182–186.
- 28.Мусаева, А (2023). РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК В МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ СРЕДЕ. Современная наука и исследования, 2(4), 182-186 <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/19208>
- 29.Kholliyev, A., & Boltayeva, Z. (2020). Resistance of cotton varieties to water deficiency. Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС, 70-72.
- 30.Холлиев, А., Махмудова, Ш., & Иргашева, Н. (2019). Меры борьбы против зерновок на зернобобовых культурах. НАУКА, ПРОИЗВОДСТВО, БИЗНЕС, 192.
- 31.Rasulov, Z. (2023). PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYADA MANIPULYATSIYA TUSHUNCHASI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 39(39).
- 32.Kholliyev, A., Boltayeva, Z., & Norboyeva, U. (2020). Cotton water exchange in water deficiency. Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС, 54-56.
- 33.Ergashovich, K. A., & Akmalovna, A. C. (2022). Soybean Cultivation Technology and Basics of Land Preparation for Planting. Eurasian Journal of Research, Development and Innovation, 7, 8-13
- 34.Rasulov, Z. (2023). The principle of cognitive economy as an important factor in information transmission. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 42(42).
- 35.Rasulov, Z. (2023). ПРИНЦИПЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ФОНАЦИОННОЙ ЭНЕРГИИ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 42(42).
- 36.Kazakova, N. N., & Sh, S. D. (2022). Evaluation of the prevalence and intensity of caries in children with rheumatism. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(5), 156-160.
- 37.Rasulov, Z., & Artikov, A. (2023, May). THE PRINCIPLE OF REDUNDANCY IN COMPOUND SENTENCES. In Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes (pp. 1-4).

- 38.Togaydullaeva, D. D. (2022). ARTERIAL GIPERTONIYA BOR BEMORLARDA KOMORBIDLIK UCHRASHI. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 32-35.
- 39.Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). THE NOTION OF NON-EQUIVALENT WORDS AND REALIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(6), 35-40.
- 40.Rasulov, Z. (2023). LISONIY TEJAMKORLIKNING AXBOROT IFODASIDAGI ORTIQCHALIKKA MUNOSABATI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 42(42).
- 41.Togaydullaeva, D. D. (2022). Erkaklarda yurak ishemik kasalligining kechishida metabolik sindrom komponentlarining ta'siri. Fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya, 1(4), 29-34.
- 42.Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC PHENOMENA OF A NATIONAL-CULTURAL NATURE, REPRESENTING MYTHOLOGICAL LINGUISTIC UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES, 2(20), 19-24.
- 43.Gafurovna, A. N., Xalimovich, M. N., & Komilovich, E. B. Z. (2023). KLIMAKTERIK YOSHDAGI AYOLLARDA ARTERIAL GIPERTENZIYANING KECHISHI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 23(6), 26-31.
- 44.Rahimova, G. (2023). МАКТАBLARDA BIOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 2, Выпуск 10, сс. 103–109). Zenodo.
- 45.Yomgirovna, R. G. (2023). AGROBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BENTONITE IN AGRICULTURE. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 3(9), 126-130.
- 46.Halimova, Y. S. (2023). Morphological Aspects of Rat Ovaries When Exposed to Caffeine Containing Drink. BEST JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT, 2(6), 294-300.
- 47.Халимова, Ю. С. (2022). МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЯИЧНИКОВ КРЫС ПРИ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИИ КОФЕИН СОДЕРЖАЩИХ НАПИТОК. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 23, 368-374.
- 48.Халимова, Ю. С., & Шокиров, Б. С. (2022). МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ООБЕННОСТИ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ АЛКОГОЛИЗМЕ. Scientific progress, 3(2), 782-789.
- 49.Halimova, Y. S. (2023). Morphofunctional Aspects of Internal Organs in Chronic Alcoholism. AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI, 2(5), 83-87.
- 50.Salokhiddinovna, X. Y. (2023). INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL FACTORS ON THE MALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 3(10), 6-13.

